

Ethnicity and Leadership in the Film "A Man Called Ahok" (Reception Analysis in Jakarta Society)

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Abstract

Basuki Tjahaja Purnama, called Ahok had shocked the politics in Indonesia. How it was not, he comes from the ethnic Chinese who became the governor of the Special Capital District of Jakarta (DKI Jakarta). In terms of ethnicity, the Chinese are a minority. Both in terms of numbers, and from the enthusiasm of participating in politics. When he was governor of DKI Jakarta in 2014-2017, all the controversy and rejection of Ahok's leadership increased. Eventually, he was jailed for a blasphemy case. This study is about the analysis of audience reception about ethnicity and leadership in the film "A Man Called Ahok". This research is important because the issue of ethnicity, especially ethnic minorities, has not been fully accepted in Indonesia. Ethnic minorities are often used as targets of hatred and enemies in case they want to run for public leadership. This research used decoding-encoding that is initiated by Stuart Hall. There are two processes namely encoding which is the process of encoding messages when the media processes the media messages, while decoding is the process of deciphering messages received by the audience. There are three categories for interpreting messages received by the audience, namely dominant, oppositional, and negotiated. This research used reception analysis with FGD data collection methods and interviews. The results showed that there was no difference between Chinese ethnicity and Javanese, Sundanese and Batak ethnicity in terms of interpreting the film "A Man Called Ahok". The message interpreted by Chinese ethnic groups was more focused on the formation of Ahok characters, while Javanese, Sundanese, and the Bataks also interpreted the message of Ahok's struggle against corruption and injustice. Acceptance in this type contains elements of adaptive and opposing, which means that the message is interpreted in negotiation.

Keywords: Film, Ethnicity, Leadership, Reception.

INTRODUCTION

Ethnicity is an interesting subject to be discussed in political leadership in Indonesia. This topic is always discussed every time before the regional head election in Indonesia. The issue of ethnicity is used as a political commodity for candidates which is sometimes used as a weapon to attack certain candidates (Burhani, 2017). That was what happened in DKI Jakarta in the 2017 election, when Basuki Tjahaja Purnama, or often called Ahok, the incumbent governor, ran for DKI Jakarta governor for the 2017-2022 period. At the time, Ahok was attacked by supporters of a candidate for governor Anies Baswedan due to ethnic reasons which are in contrast to the majority of ethnic groups in Jakarta.

Ahok was a phenomenal governor, he had several policies that were different from other governors, one of the policies was budget transparency. He also revitalized the flow of the Ciliwung river by relocating residents living on the riverbanks. For all his work, he won 14 awards including the Anti-Gratification Governor of the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) and the Governor with the best and innovative planning from the 2016 National Planning Agency (Bapenas).

He was born and raised on Belitung Island from a Chinese family. His family is friendly and mingle with the community. They are very concerned about the social conditions of the region and their hometown. Ahok grew up in a family of tin and nickel entrepreneurs. His father owned a mining company but he was often the target of extortion by corrupt officials. Ahok followed his father as a mining entrepreneur, but the perpetrators of the corrupt officials kept their businesses from developing. Based on this problem, Ahok turned out to be a politician.

His political career was like a roller coaster, uphill then dipping sharply. Starting from being a regent in East Belitung Regency then becoming a member of the House of People's Representatives from the Gerindra Party and becoming the Governor of DKI Jakarta. At the end of his position, Ahok was serving a prison sentence of 2 years for being proven to insult religion. Ahok's journey to politics is certainly due to his ability to carry out political communication. According to Syaifuddin (2019: 419) states that political communication can be in the form of messages that have a political impact from the political authorities to the community or the delivery of support or demands by the community for political authorities.

Ahok's political journey experienced pros and cons. He was rejected by various elements of the community because of his Chinese ethnicity and Christianity, but he was still loved by the Jakarta community because of his firmness and struggle to improve public services in DKI Jakarta. It was also what prompted Ilya Sigma, Emir Hakim and Reza Hidayat to produce the film "A Man Called Ahok" based on Basuki Thajaja Purnama's autobiography book 'A man called Ahok': a piece of the story of struggle & sincerity by Rudi Valinka. The book tells the life of Ahok from childhood until he became a Regent in East Belitung.

The film is directed by Putrama Tuta with the main star Daniel Mananta plays as the adult Ahok and Eric Febrian as the young Ahok. In addition, a series of other actors in this film include Denny Sumargo, Chew Kin Wah, Sita Nursanti, Donny Damara, Ferry Salim, Eriska Rein, and Jill Gladys. The film shooting process is mostly located in Belitung and runs for 37 days from March to April 2018 (Wirastama, 2018; Setiawan, 2018).

The film began airing simultaneously in cinemas all over Indonesia on November 8, 2018, and the ticket sales reached 1.3 million until the end of November 2018 (Tirto.id). Although only ranked 12th best-selling Indonesian films throughout 2018, this film won 5 awards at the 2019 Indonesian Indonesian Box Office Movie Award (IBOMA) namely, Best Newcomer Actor (Eric Febrian who played the role of Little Ahok), Best Trailer, Cast Best Supporting Men (Donny Damara), Best Lead Actor (Denny Sumargo who plays Ahok's father) and Best Director, Putrama Tuta (liputan6.com).

The formulation of the problems are "how is the audience reception of the film "A Man Called Ahok"? "Do the film "A Man Called Ahok" causes a change in the audience's view of Basuki Tjahaja Purnama? The purpose of this study is to unravel the audience's reception about Ahok after watching the film.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The research using the reception method has received attention from communication science academics. Although the reception method is relatively old, this concept is the antithesis of audience study research that uses a quantitative approach. This method has been applied by Angela D'Egidio (2015), Kevin Smets (2012), Patricipa Caille (2010), Belinda Flores Espiritu (2011), Bouziane Zaid (2014), Joy L. Johnson, John L. Oliffe, Mary T Kelly, Joan L. Bottorff, and Karen LeBeau (2009),

Angela D'Egidio conducted a 2015 study entitled *How Readers Perceive Translated Literary Works: An Analysis of Reader Reception*. In her study, she investigates the reception of readers of translated literary texts to explore the expectations of readers about literary works. For this purpose, three forms of online English, American and Italian book reviews commented on the English version of Andrea Camilleri 'La forma dell'acqua' (The Shape of Water) and in the Italian version of Stephen King Joyland 'were collected and analyzed. This analysis showed that the acceptance of translated texts by Anglo-American and Italian readers is different, in terms of focus and perception.

Kevin Smets in 2012 made a study entitled *Connecting Islam and Film Culture: The Reception of the Message (Ar Risala) Among the Moroccan Diaspora*. The research method used was an ethnographic study with in-depth interview data collection techniques and FGD. The results showed that film preferences and consumption varied greatly in socio-demographic and linguistic. However, one particular religious film, the status of a cult, *Ar Risalah (The Message)*, a 1976 historical epic produced by Mustapha Akkad which discussed the life of the Prophet Muhammad. The local distribution of the film is discussed, as well as its acceptance among the Moroccan diaspora. By identifying three positions with respect to Islam, different modes of acceptance are found, from distant and objective to transparent and subjective modes. It is found that the film supports the teaching of religion between generations, in the context of families and mosques. In addition, special inspirational messages are taken from films by those who seek a well-defined space for Islam in their own lives.

Patricipa Caille's 2010 study entitled *A Tunisian Film Festival in Paris: Issues in Reception at the Intersection of French and Anglo-American Approaches to Cultural Analysis of the Diasporas*. The research method used was reception analysis with data collection techniques using informal questionnaires. The results showed an analysis of responses to informal questionnaires highlighting the ways in which viewers participated and were involved, without clear contradictions, both in traditional values related to film culture in France and in strong attachments to Tunisian films that were not always valued in the same film culture.

The study conducted by Belinda Flores Espiritu (2011) with the title Transnational Audience Reception as a Theater of Struggle: Young Filipino Women's Reception of Korean Television Dramas. The research method used was FGD. In her study, she found the results that although there were FGD participants who adapted global capitalist values, which showed that they favored the domain of Western cultural hegemony, most FGD participants articulated Negotiated Reading of capitalist values and Oppositional Reading in terms of the dominant ideology of patriarchy capitalist. In interpreting Korean dramas, young women identify the social pathology of poverty, class inequality, and capitalist patriarchal values and develop emancipatory discourse related to these matters.

The study conducted by Bouziane Zaid in 2014 entitled Audience Reception Analysis of Moroccan Public Service Broadcasting. The research method used was FGD. In his research, he found the application of Stuart Hall's theory in the Moroccan context revealed some of the strengths of the model and some of its limitations. Although this model provides analytical instruments that help us understand the relationship between how television producers encode messages and how audiences decode messages, this study illustrates the limitations of applying Hall theory to non-western audiences. Hall's model is based on the assumption that audiences are able to decode television content and based on variations in the decoding process are the result of audience reactions to hegemonic messages. The study found that this did not apply to Moroccan audiences and that additional theoretical instruments were needed for the analysis of audience acceptance to be complete and substantial.

The study conducted by Joy L. Johnson, John L. Oliffe, Mary T. Kelly, Joan L. Bottorff, and Karen LeBeau in 2009 entitled The Readings of Smoking Fathers: A Reception Analysis of Tobacco Cessation Images. The research method used was content analysis and in-depth interviews. The research findings highlight how most men negotiate or oppose the dominant health discourse that communicates the dangers of smoking by reproducing the dominant ideals of masculinity, including ignoring self-health explicitly. They accept the dominant social discourse about fathers who reproduce traditional ideas about masculinity, such as protectors and providers. It was concluded that the form of prevention interventions targeted for cigarette use for new fathers must (a) develop more awareness about the ability of audiences to choose discourses that empower their own interpretive positions with regard to the media, and (b) deconstruct masculine contexts to avoid giving reasons to continue cigarette consumption.

This study is different from previous studies. The previous research did not raise the issue of ethnicity and leadership and did not interview message producers (film directors) while researchers interviewed message producers to find out the purpose of filmmaking. As for the methodology of this study used reception analysis concepts from Stuart Hall.

Ethnicity

Ethnicity is briefly defined as ethnic groups. According to Karl W. Deutsch, the growth of a nation-state often occurs through the process of combining ethnic groups (ethnicity) into a nation. When explaining about the nation and national integration, he further states that: "a nation is a result of the transformation of a people, or several ethnic elements, in the process of social mobilization" or, for its translation, a nation is the result of the transformation of people, or from several ethnic elements, in the process of social mobilization (Deutsch, 1984). Historical facts in Indonesia also state that before the Dutch colonial government implemented a bureaucratic system, plantations, transportation facilities, and modern education in the 19th century, the Indonesian community lived in an awareness of ethnicity. This awareness only covers certain areas with social categories such as ethnicity, religion, and language which are also limited.

Erin Blakemore (2019) distinguishes the definition of race and ethnicity. Race is defined as a category of human beings who share certain physical characteristics. While ethnicity is broadly defined as a large group of people classified according to general categories such as race, nationality, ethnicity, religion, linguistics, or cultural origin or background. The race is usually associated with biological aspects and is associated with physical characteristics such as skin color or hair texture. Ethnicity is associated with cultural expression and identification. However, both are social constructs used to categorize and characterize populations that appear different.

Ethnicity and political studies are not a new thing in Indonesia. History proves that the two rebellion movements in the Old Order era were triggered by ethnicity issues, namely the Ratu Adil Army (APRA) on January 23, 1950, a movement to maintain the federal form of the Pasundan federal state and the Republic of South Maluku Rebellion (RMS). In the First Election of the Republic of Indonesia in 1955, the issue of

ethnicity and identity was not sold, it was proven that there were no political parties based on ethnicity that succeed. Ethnic issues were less echoed than issues of revolution and anti-colonialism. The victory of Nasional Indonesia Party or called PNI in the 1955 elections showed that the campaign for national identity and the spirit of colonialism was more acceptable than ethnic and identity issues (Sofyan Sjaf, 2014)

During the New Order, there was no issue of ethnicity completely. No one party carried the issue of ethnicity. The three parties at that time, namely the Persatuan Pembangunan Party (PPP), Golongan Karya, and the Demokrasi Indonesia Party (PDI) did not address ethnic issues in any of their political campaigns. Electoral system factors that used a system of representation rather than direct elections made ethnicity issues increasingly did not exist. Ethnicity only began to reverberate again in the 2009 elections, this was evident from the statement of the Chairperson of the Persatuan Pembangunan Party Bachtiar Chamsyah who said that "how could I become president, I'm not a Javanese." Bachtiar's statement was published in the Rakyat Merdeka daily on March 11, 2008. Bachtiar's statement seemed to make a dichotomy that only Javanese deserve to be president, other than Java is inappropriate. The issue of ethnicity increasingly took place when regional autonomy began to be implemented in 2005 where "Putra Daerah" (ethnic majority) became the main factor seen if someone wanted to advance in the Regional Election (Pilkada)

Reception Analysis

Reception is a theory that audiences are active people who bring all their values and experiences in interacting with the mass media. Reception analysis is a flow of modern cultural studies developed to understand polysemy as an interpretation of the text. The meaning conducted by the community is known as reception studies or reception analysis which refers to the "interpretive community" (Downing, et.al, 1995: 214, Pertti Alasuutari, 1999) to describe the collection of people who make interpretations. The pioneers of this consumption study assume that whatever analysis of textual meaning is carried out as a critique, it is still far from certainty about the identified meaning, which can only be activated by the reader or audience or consumers.

The community has a weak position in the eyes of the media because it tends only to accept what is offered by the media and then make an active interpretation of the sign received. This is in line with the nature of media polysemy which is open to interpretation. With this interpretation, the majority of the audience routinely modifies or changes the dominant ideology that is reflected by the contents of the media so that it is following the development of society and the development of the media itself.

Message recipients are active producers of meaning that are free of the experience they feel when receiving and interpreting texts. This meaning framework is expressed by Stuart Hall in terms of Encoding - Decoding (ED). The ED model focuses on the relationship between the message the producer constructs and the interpretation of the message built by the recipient audience. These two processes are very related because they involve the same media text. However, the results of interpretation are not necessarily the same as what producers want to convey at the beginning of its formation (Stuart Hall in Durham and Kellner, 2006 p. 163).

According to Hall in Barker (2004) the production of meaning does not ensure the consumption of meaning as intended by the encoder because television messages carry a variety of meanings and can be interpreted in different ways. Therefore, Hall explains three models in giving meaning to television, namely: 1) Hegemonic code is one of the systems or codes generated when the social situation surrounding the audience receives the desired meaning (preferred reading), 2) The negotiation code is a system or code that is negotiated. In this case, the dominant values and structures that are in preferred readings are accepted, but these values are used as an affirmation that the existing social situation needs to be improved based on a particular situation, and 3) The Oppositional Code (Oppositional Readings), is a system or code which rejects the dominant version and social values of preferred readings. The audience places messages in systems of meaning that are radically opposed to dominant meanings.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a qualitative research type with a reception analysis method. Reception analysis is an acceptance study or acceptance analysis developed by Stuart Hall of the Center for Contemporary Cultural Studies (CCCS), University of Birmingham. According to Hall (in Baran & Davis, 2013), reception analysis is an audience-based theory that aims to see how different members of the audience with different backgrounds and traits, give meaning to a particular form of content. Hall considers that in conducting a

reception analysis, a researcher should focus on the social and political context in content production, and also the consumption of media content (interpretation) (Baran & Davis, 2013).

The focus in an audience study is the ability of active audiences, namely the audience positioned as consumers and producers of meaning. According to Chris Barker (2005), active audiences are seen in terms of the ability of the audience to be a creator of meaning, and not just a passive recipient of messages offered by the text. The audience is not a homogeneous mass, but a heterogeneous mass consisting of a variety of cultural competencies. So, people with different backgrounds will certainly interpret the message in different ways.

The researchers used data collection techniques by FGD (*Focus Group Discussion*). In the implementation of the FGD, the researchers conducted open and targeted discussions with the discussion participants. The open discussion in question was that, there were no indicators of right or wrong answers from the discussion participants, but each participant felt free in expressing their views on the film "A Man Called Ahok". The researchers also conducted interviews with respondents. When a research discussion, the researchers found an unclear explanation. 20 discussion participants with the following characteristics:

Informant	Sex	Age	Ethnicity	Religion
A	Female	28	Javanese	Animism
B	Male	38	Sundanese	Animism
C	Male	38	Sundanese	Islam
D	Female	37	Batak	Protestant
E	Male	39	Javanese	Islam
F	Male	35	Batak	Protestant
G	Male	51	Chinese	Catholic
H	Female	24	Chinese	Christian
I	Female	51	Jakarta	Christian
J	Male	54	Javanese	Islam
K	Female	47	Batak	Protestant
L	Female	47	Batak	Protestant
M	Male	46	Chinese	Protestant
N	Male	70	Chinese	Protestant
O	Female	29	Chinese	Protestant
P	Female	25	Javanese	Protestant
Q	Male	45	Javanese	Islam
R	Female	36	Chinese	Catholic
S	Male	28	Chinese	Agnostic
T	Female	24	Batak	Christian

DISCUSSION

This study analyzes the reception of the film audience "A Man Called Ahok" for Jakarta ID-card employees, viewed from the perspective of the Encoding-Decoding theory. This theory focuses on the role of the audience in receiving messages, not on the role of the sender of the message (Danesi, 2013). In theory explained by Stuart Hall (1974), the audience not only receives the message conveyed by the sender of the message but can also reproduce the message conveyed.

To get a full picture of the film, this study began with an interview with director Putrama Tuta to find out what message was to be conveyed in making the film "A Man Called Ahok". The aim is to assist researchers in mapping the actual audience reception so that it can be determined whether the reception is in the dominant, negotiating, or alternative or opposition categories.

According to Putrama Tuta, the making of the film "A Man Called Ahok" actually has no political context. Its main purpose is not to portray Ahok's way of life from a teenager, to become a leader. Tuta also admitted that the film does not highlight the ethnic minority aspects that were successful in becoming leaders. The message to be conveyed is a depiction of the humanism side of how the struggle of a child is educated by his father with a hard and disciplined upbringing so that the child succeeds in becoming a leader. This film only tells about Ahok's relationship with the family that is not widely known. Ahok's process of being involved in politics was only told in a flash. While his love story with Veronica Tan is also not presented in this film.

The results of interviews with the audience of the film "A Man Called Ahok", showed that the messages captured by them are varied. When asked for an opinion on the description of Ahok's leadership in the film "A Man Called Ahok". The Chinese male informant argued that the picture of Ahok's leadership in the film is the same as the real Ahok, but it is rather illustrated how Ahok grew up. Ahok is described as a leader who prioritizes other people's interests. According to G informant there is not much difference, the film just depicts his youth so he tends not to think about the consequences of the decisions taken. Then he tends to be rushed in making decisions. The Chinese female informant, when asked about Ahok's leadership picture in the film, argued that the film does not depict Ahok's leadership, but is quite similar to Ahok who actually prioritizes other people over his interests and also upholds inter-ethnic equality:

The Javanese male informant also gave a similar answer, he said that Ahok's leadership is depicted by the figure of a young man who works hard, struggle for his rights, creative, a strict leader, and anti-corruption, following Ahok's real figure.

The Batak female informant argued that the picture of Ahok's leadership in the film is depicted by anti-corruption, hard-working, responsible, assertive, honest, and professional figures. It can be underlined that most of the opinions of the four categories of informants about the description of Ahok's leadership in the film "A Man Called Ahok" are positive.

When asked for opinions on the description of Chinese ethnicity, the Chinese male informant argued that the picture of Ahok's ethnicity in the film is depicted as someone who still adheres to Chinese ethnic culture, but still contributes to the nation. Ethnicity is not too highlighted properly described. The challenges and struggles experienced by Ahok as an ethnic Chinese in trying to contribute to the nation are the same as the challenges of the struggles of other Chinese communities.

The Chinese female informant argued that the picture of ethnicity in this film is to hold Chinese cultural values, but still be nationalist and patriotic. This film depicts equality between ethnic Chinese and natives. Although it still has Chinese cultural values, patriotism about its Indonesian-based humanity is more prominent.

Whereas the Javanese male informant held the same opinion, that the picture of Ahok's ethnicity in that film is not too highlighted, although it is depicted that Chinese ethnicity is less acceptable in the government field. However, in the life of the Malays, ethnic Chinese communities can mingle with others. According to J in his village, Ahok is portrayed as not showing his ethnicity, Ahok makes good friends with the people around him. Ahok feels no stranger to the Malay community.

The Javanese female informant also argued that in the film "A Man Called Ahok", the picture of ethnicity in the film is depicted by ethnic Chinese who are able to mingle with other ethnicities, even though Ahok's family is quite attached to the ethnic Chinese. Ahok has a nationalist spirit and he does not discriminate against ethnicity. It can be concluded that most of the opinions of the four categories of informants about the description of Ahok's ethnicity in the film "A Man Called Ahok" were positive.

When asked for opinions on the accuracy of the description of Ahok in the film "A Man Called Ahok", the Chinese male informant argued that it is quite accurate, but Ahok's character is more dependable and controversial, because this film is more describing the influence of Ahok's father in forming Ahok's personality. The filmmakers are considered to take a safer way in making the film so that it does not emphasize Ahok's ethnicity which in reality is controversial: "It seems the director of the filmmaker wants to play it safe so that the description of Ahok's ethnicity is not too contrast or controversial" as S said.

Meanwhile, when asked about the accuracy of Ahok's image in the film, the Chinese female informant thought that it is less accurate because it is only depicted a little character, and only focused on the formation of his character: "It is not exactly 100% accurate because there are still very few images and only the beginning of the formation of his character" said O.

The Sundanese male informant also shared the same opinion that the accuracy of Ahok's description is not entirely accurate because it is only raised the lives of Ahok and his family in Bangka Belitung. But Ahok's personality is quite accurate, although Ahok's description tends to be perfect. According to "B" "this film only elevates the lives of Ahok and his family when they lived in the Bangka Belitung Islands.

The Batak ethnic female informant argued that the accuracy of Ahok's description in the film is quite accurate, according to what is often displayed by the mass media in general: "It's quite accurate but there are still some personal stories of Ahok that are not yet known to common people, such as Ahok's persistent and sincere personality" Said T. It can be underlined that most of the opinions of the four categories of

informants about the accuracy of the description of Ahok in the film "A Man Called Ahok" were positive but not completely accurate.

The Chinese male informant argued that the message delivered focused on forming Ahok's character who has a good personality and loves Indonesia despite many challenges. He said that Ahok is honest and diligent in his struggle. While the Chinese female informant captured the main message, as follows:

1. The experiences from the past and education of parents give a strong influence on character formation.
2. We must help other people without seeing the ethnicity
3. To get rid of bad habits that have formed before, innovation and bravery are needed.

Where the Javanese, Sundanese, Batak male informants captured the main messages, as follows:

1. Dealing with corrupt officials is very difficult;
2. Honesty is needed for truth, humanity, and justice;
3. Youth must never retreat because the current struggle can form the future,
4. Ahok is a good leader and firm in his attitude, especially towards injustice. He can show a good example to the community,
5. Ethnic Chinese can be part of the government

While the Javanese, Sundanese and Batak female informants captured six main messages, as follows :

1. Ahok wants to fight injustice and corruption so he turned to the government;
2. Chinese ethnic is part of the Indonesian people who live side by side with the whole community. They help one another;
3. Ahok's characters are honest, brave and firm. It should be an example for others;
4. Ahok's family supports each other. It deserves to be an example;
5. Welfare is the right of all people, so we must strive to live better lives with the determination and strategy to develop Indonesia;
6. Helping people does not mean reducing blessings, but can add blessings.

Although not all audiences catch the same message, they all agree with the message they capture. Almost all audiences agree that the description of Ahok in this film is accurate according to the actual Ahok. Therefore, it can be concluded that the reception of the audience is included in the category of Negotiations, which according to Marris and Thornham (1996) means the audience understands enough what is displayed by the media, but not all are interpreted the same. Acceptance in this type contains elements of adaptive and opposition, which means that the message is negotiated.

CONCLUSION

Not all audiences catch the same message, but all audiences agree with the message they capture in the film "A Man Called Ahok". Audience reception is included in the category of Negotiations, which means the audience understands enough what is displayed by the media, but not all messages are interpreted the same by the source. Acceptance in this type contains elements of adaptive and opposing, which means that the message is interpreted in negotiation. There was no difference between audiences of Chinese ethnicity and Javanese, Sundanese and Batak ethnicity in terms of interpreting the film "A Man Called Ahok". The message captured by Chinese ethnics was more centered on the formation of Ahok characters, while Javanese, Sundanese and Batak sources also captured the message of Ahok's struggle against corruption and injustice. The informants did not feel a change in their views on Ahok before and after watching the film "A Man Called Ahok." They were only admitted that they had gained knowledge about Ahok's background.

REFERENCES

- i. D'egiodio, "How readers perceive translated literary works: An analysis of reader reception," *Lingue e Linguaggi*, vol. 14, 2015.
- ii. Ahmad Najib Burhani, *Ethnic Minority Politics in Jakarta's Gubernatorial Election*, RESEARCHERS AT ISEAS – YUSOF ISHAK INSTITUTE ANALYSE CURRENT EVENTS, Juni 207.
- iii. F. Espiritu, "Transnational audience reception as a theater of struggle: young Filipino women's reception of Korean television dramas," *Asian J. Commun.*, vol. 4, pp. 355–372, 2011.
- iv. Baran, S. J., & Davis, D. K. (2013). *Teori Komunikasi Massa: Dasar, Pergolakan, dan Masa Depan*. Jakarta: Salemba Humanika

- v. Bouziane Zaid (2014), *Audience reception analysis of Moroccan public service broadcasting*. *Middle East Journal of Culture and Communication*, 7(3), 284-309.
- vi. Barker, *Cultural Studies: Teori & Praktek*. Yogyakarta: Kreasi Wacana, 2004.
- vii. Downing, John, D.H, et.all *Questioning the Media: A Critical Introduction*. Sage Publication, 1995.
- viii. Durham, Meenakshi Gigi, et.all, *Media and Cultural Studies: Key Works*. Blackwell Publishing, 2006.
- ix. Blakemore, "Race and ethnicity: How are they different," *National Geographic*.2019
- x. Joy L. Johnson, dkk *The readings of smoking fathers: a reception analysis of tobacco cessation images*. *Health communication*, 24(6), 532-547.
- xi. Karl W. Deutsch, *Nationalism and Social Communication*. MIT Press, 1966.
- xii. P. Alasuutari, *Rethinking the Media Audience: The New Age*. Sage Publication.
- xiii. P. Caille, "A Tunisian film festival in Paris: issues in reception at the intersection of French and Anglo-American approaches to cultural analysis of the diasporas.," *French Cult. Stud.*, vol. 2, pp. 85-96, 2010.
- xiv. S. Purnomo, "A Man Called Ahok Raih Trailer Film Terbaik IBOMA 2019," *liputan6.com*, 2018.
- xv. S. Sjaf, *Politik Etnik*. Jakarta: Yayasan Pustaka Obor, 2014.
- xvi. Syaifuddin, *The Influence Of Political Exposure In Digital Media To The Participation Of Prospective Voters For Demokrat Party In East Java Ahead Of The Election 2019*. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Volume 9, Issue 12, December 2019